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The future of precision oncology and Artificial Intelligence in Belgium: scenarios and policy responses

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Conflicts of Interest

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Abstract

Purpose: Precision medicine, also known as personalized medicine, enables the provision of tailored health services to patients. In the prevention, early detection, and treatment of cancers, precision medicine is highly promising, given the increasing use of genomic profiling for diagnosis and adapting therapies in several tumor types. Artificial Intelligence (AI) can support this process by analyzing vast amounts of relevant data. However, high-quality data and financial investments in the health system are essential for the implementation of precision medicine and AI solutions in routine cancer care.

Approach: Building on the quantitative outcomes of a foresight exercise published in another study, this article collects qualitative data to gain more detailed insights into the future of precision oncology in Belgium and discusses the role of AI in this field. It reports the results of a series of expert workshops, focusing on four hypothetical future scenarios that are centered around technological and economic issues that must be overcome for the widespread use of precision oncology in Belgium.

Findings: The study concludes that all four scenarios discussed in the workshops would require supportive policy measures in Belgium, which should go beyond mere technological and economic considerations, such as involving patient associations and the public in policy design or creating multi-disciplinary expert groups for precision medicine.

Originality: To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to employ foresight methodology to illustrate possible future scenarios, scrutinize feasible approaches for implementing precision oncology in Belgium, and discuss the use of AI in this context.

Keywords

precision oncology, Artificial Intelligence, foresight, scenario building, Belgium

1 Purpose

Precision medicine, also known as personalized medicine or genomic medicine, uses genomic profiling of humans to identify actionable mutations or biomarkers and matches treatments to biological abnormalities (Levit *et al.*, 2019). The use of genomic biomarkers is a key driver of precision medicine, whereas genomic testing predicts disease risk, prognosis, and patient response to guide tailored treatment decisions (Pataky *et al.*, 2022). Enabled by recent insights gained from the whole genome sequencing (WGS) technology, the importance of precision medicine is rapidly growing in health systems (Johnson *et al.*, 2021). As a subset of precision medicine, precision oncology is highly promising in the treatment or early detection of cancers (Pashayan *et al.*, 2020). With advancements in tumor analysis through next-generation sequencing (NGS), molecular diagnostics, and targeted therapies, the use of precision oncology is continuously evolving to address the rising incidence of cancer worldwide (Malone *et al.*, 2020).

Indeed, with the increasing use of genomic profiling for diagnosis and therapy personalization in various tumor types, precision oncology is transforming routine cancer care in different health systems (Mateo *et al.*, 2022). For instance, the All of Us research program in the United States of America (USA), launched by the National Institutes of Health (NIH), aims to advance precision medicine by analyzing diverse health data to understand how lifestyle, environment, and genetics influence health outcomes (NIH, 2024). Based on successful results of such projects, precision medicine is increasingly being integrated in the standard care of patients with advanced cancer in the USA (Levit *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, the 100,000 Genomes Project in the United Kingdom (UK), delivered by the National Health Service (NHS) and Genomics England, laid the foundations for NHS Genomic Medicine Service, making England the first national health system to offer WGS as part of routine care (NHS England, 2022). In the European Union (EU), similar initiatives have been taking place. Most notably, the Europe's Beating Cancer Plan (EBCP), which aims to improve the prevention, detection, treatment, and management of cancer, prioritizes access to precision oncology and promote large-scale sharing of genomic data in the EU (Mateo *et al.*, 2022). In this context, and as part of the EU's digital health improvement plan, the '1+ Million Genomes' (1+MG) flagship initiative lays the foundation for sharing genetic data securely across 25 EU countries, along with the UK and Norway (European Commission, 2023).

Belgium is taking important steps towards precision oncology, both by participating in European initiatives and through its independent efforts (Van Valckenborgh *et al.*, 2018; Schmitt, Delnord, *et al.*, 2024; Schmitt, Poirel, *et al.*, 2024). In 2015, major Belgian stakeholders (public bodies for health service provision, patient associations and health insurance funds) published a report on the feasibility of the integration of NGS into clinical practice for (haemato-)oncology in Belgium. This feasibility study was then translated into a guide that described the major actions to be taken to introduce NGS in clinical settings. In 2016, the publication entitled “Introduction of Next-Generation Sequencing in routine diagnostics in oncology and haemato-oncology in Belgium” was officially approved by the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health (WIV-ISP, 2016). Following the approval, several projects have been initiated since then, including i) the Personalized Medicine Commission (ComPerMed), which brings relevant experts together to work on this topic; ii) the External Quality Assessment (EQA) project, which sets a national framework for external quality assessments for NGS analyses in Belgium; and iii) a real-life pilot study that has been conducted with NGS networks and the National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance (NIHDI) at the federal level. Despite these promising steps, major hurdles remain to make precision oncology a reality in routine care in Belgium, particularly due to technological and budgetary challenges (Schmitt, Delnord, *et al.*, 2024).

The future of cancer care is set to be transformed by the emergence of vast data derived from NGS, algorithm-driven image processing, comprehensive electronic health records, extensive clinical trials, and advanced disease prediction models (Dlamini *et al.*, 2020). Precision oncology ultimately depends on processing and analyzing large datasets to identify specific molecular patterns that can guide individualized care and dedicated resources in the health system to enable this process (Dlamini *et al.*, 2022). However, obtaining high-quality data and analyzing extensive datasets can be challenging and time-consuming. The primary strength of Artificial Intelligence (AI) lies in its capacity to analyze large datasets, allowing treatments to be tailored to individual medical histories and needs. For instance, developing a digital twin (a virtual model of a patient to personalize care) involves collecting and linking comprehensive information on a patient’s lifestyle and biology, and leveraging AI is essential to handle such a vast amount of data for effective cancer management (Dlamini *et al.*, 2022). In practice, however, the use of AI in precision oncology requires addressing several major challenges, such as dealing with multiple data modalities, insufficient data, and issues with explainability of AI models (Azuaje, 2019). In addition, integrating precision oncology into routine care

means substantial financial investments to establish and maintain the digital infrastructure for necessary data flow between institutions.

In Belgium (a federal state with a health system based on compulsory insurance through social contributions), healthcare policies focus on accessibility, quality, and efficiency, supported by strategies like integrated care, expertise concentration, patient care trajectories, and ongoing efforts in digitalizing health information and data sharing (Gerken and Merkur, 2024). Against this background, we aim to understand with this study how precision oncology can be implemented in the Belgian health system in the next few years and discuss the use of AI in this context. Our main research question is as follows: “What could be major challenges against integrating precision oncology in the Belgian health system in different future scenarios, and what policy responses can be developed to address these challenges?”—we explore hypothetical scenarios that combine varying levels of technological developments, which could enable more effective data usage, with different levels of budgetary commitment for precision medicine. The manuscript is thus structured around four future scenarios, each detailing the associated challenges and policy strategies for the integration of precision oncology in the Belgian health system. Each scenario is followed by a summary table that synthesizes the outcomes.

Generally speaking, rich qualitative data through foresight help in identifying possible risks and opportunities in a particular domain, supporting strategic decision-making in complex and uncertain environments. The use of foresight scenarios thus may allow researchers to envision potential future developments under different conditions, offering valuable insights into the implications of budgetary and technological barriers to implement innovative solutions in health systems. Indeed, this approach is widely applied in health policy and technology assessments to identify challenges, clarify future scenarios, and evaluate the feasibility of new treatments and technologies, making it particularly valuable for rapidly evolving fields like AI (Alon *et al.*, 2025). While scenario building for foresight usually provides a useful framework for anticipating future needs and making informed policy decisions, this methodology has also some limitations, such as the inherent uncertainty of predicting long-term outcomes and the challenge of capturing all relevant variables to include in the scenarios. As such, our study is an initial step to identify critical points for further research in this underexplored field and lay the groundwork for more informed decisions about the future of precision oncology and AI in Belgium.

2 Methodology

Within a mixed-methods study, this article forms the final part of an explanatory sequential design. Explanatory sequential design is a commonly used research method that unfolds in two phases (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018): First, quantitative data are collected and analyzed to identify relevant key patterns. This is then followed by a qualitative phase where data are collected to provide deeper insights, explanations, or context for the results obtained in the quantitative phase. This study design is widely used as it allows researchers to begin with a broad overview through quantitative methods and then delve into more specific, nuanced understandings through qualitative exploration. By integrating these two approaches, the explanatory sequential design offers a comprehensive approach for addressing complex research questions. This article reports qualitative insights, building upon the quantitative data gathered in the initial phase of our foresight exercise (Schmitt, Delnord, *et al.*, 2024). It presents the findings from two expert workshops that were integral to a comprehensive foresight analysis on the implementation of precision oncology in Belgium, guided by the Work Package “Foresight: Modelling and Scenarios” of the European project Population Health Information Research Infrastructure (PHIRI).

The quantitative data from an expert survey (Schmitt, Delnord, *et al.*, 2024) served as a foundation for the development of future scenarios in this article. The expert survey had highlighted key considerations such as rising cancer cases and healthcare expenditures in Belgium, challenges in advanced Information Technology (IT) solutions for data transfer, and demand for high-quality data for precision medicine, which built the basis of the discussions in our foresight workshops. As such, these key factors allowed workshop participants to explore how precision medicine could evolve in different future scenarios and helped them formulate challenges and policy responses to facilitate the successful integration of precision oncology in the Belgian health system. To this aim, two foresight workshops were organized on 6 April 2023 and 5 May 2023 with the participation of country experts within the field of precision medicine and genomics. The invitations were sent to 28 experts across Belgium, who had expressed their willingness to take part in the workshops in the foresight survey conducted (Schmitt, Delnord, *et al.*, 2024). In total, 14 of them (50%) confirmed their participation to the foresight workshops (Table 1).

Table 1. Experts participating in the study (Source: Authors' own work)

Field	Number of experts
Academia/research organization	5
University hospital	4
Industry	3
National cancer registry	1
Patient organization	1

The aim of the first workshop was to ensure that the country experts discussed and reached a consensus on the major driving forces for precision oncology in Belgium, based on the quantitative outcomes of the foresight survey (Schmitt, Delnord, *et al.*, 2024). Identified through the survey results, participants validated the main contextual issues concerning precision oncology in Belgium, leading to the development of hypothetical future scenarios (achieved by the moderator after the workshop). The 2x2 scenario method combined two key uncertainties—Budget (low-high) and Technology (low-high)—to create four distinct scenarios. Each axis represented one spectrum: Budget for financial resources, and Technology for the level of technological advancement to enable precision oncology in the Belgian health system. Their intersection formed four quadrants for four future scenarios: 1. low budget, low technology; 2. low budget, high technology; 3. high budget, low technology; 4. high budget, high technology (Table 2).

Table 2. Four foresight scenarios (Source: Authors' own work)

Scenario 1: low budget, low technology	Scenario 2: low budget, high technology	Scenario 3: high budget, low technology	Scenario 4: high budget, high technology
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of allocated budget for precision medicine in the healthcare system • Low quality of data; lack of IT solutions that could allow the transfer of data to a secure platform; low speed of digitalization that could foster health data exchange; low standardization of protocols, tests and nomenclature across hospitals and laboratories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of allocated budget for precision medicine in the healthcare system • Sufficient quality of data; sufficient IT solutions that could allow the transfer of data to a secure platform; sufficient speed of digitalization that could foster health data exchange; sufficient standardization of protocols, tests and nomenclature across hospitals and laboratories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sufficient allocated budget for precision medicine in the healthcare system • Low quality of data; lack of IT solutions that could allow the transfer of data to a secure platform; low speed of digitalization that could foster health data exchange; low standardization of protocols, tests and nomenclature across hospitals and laboratories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sufficient allocated budget for precision medicine in the healthcare system • Sufficient quality of data; sufficient IT solutions that could allow the transfer of data to a secure platform; sufficient speed of digitalization that could foster health data exchange; sufficient standardization of protocols, tests and nomenclature across hospitals and laboratories

These scenarios were then presented to the participants in a second workshop to gather qualitative data to complete the foresight exercise. With the help of a collaborative online whiteboard platform, Miro, the same country experts formulated challenges and developed different policy responses to the challenges faced in each of the four scenarios. To be more precise, the experts individually listed potential challenges on Miro, making their notes visible to all workshop participants. These notes were collectively reviewed and openly discussed in the group, with experts asking clarifying questions to each other and the moderator merging

similar content while refining weaker ones with the agreement of experts. The same procedure was applied for the formulation of policy strategies. After the workshop, the outcomes were summarized and circulated within the group as a draft document, asking for the approval and where necessary further feedback of the workshop participants. No objections were raised to the draft document, enabling the finalization of the study results. In the following section, we present the qualitative outcomes of the foresight exercise, derived from this second and final workshop.

3 Findings

3.1 Scenario 1 (low budget, low technology)

3.1.1 Challenges of Scenario 1

Experts agree that the current situation in Belgium is reflected most in the first scenario, meaning a lack of allocated budget and technology for precision oncology. The Belgian Cancer Registry (BCR) is the main recipient of data on all new cancer diagnoses, in compliance with the legal requirement for all hospitals participating in an oncology care program and providing services for pathological anomalies. However, information gathered by the BCR is often insufficiently detailed for the purpose of modifying policies or treatment protocols. Precision oncology requires data standardization to facilitate collaborative initiatives among multiple entities. Ideally, for every clinical situation, a standardized testing methodology should be in place across all hospital types, irrespective of their size or location in Belgium. Otherwise, each hospital follows a different approach, leading to a lack of harmonization in protocols, tests, and nomenclature. A serious challenge in Belgium is the obligation for hospitals to submit patient data to different platforms for different purposes. When hospitals and the government store data in separate files, the process of data transfer becomes time-consuming in the absence of batch transfer, and the interpretation of data remains complicated.

3.1.2 Policy strategies for Scenario 1

Currently, precision medicine in Belgium falls within the remit of Sciensano's work, exemplified by initiatives such as the ComPerMed (Sciensano, 2023). The ComPerMed operates effectively, comprising a diverse team of experts from various institutions and disciplines (e.g. pathologists, geneticists, and oncologists). This broad coalition enables Sciensano to gain wider contextual perspectives and provide answers pertinent to precision

medicine. In this first scenario, it could be beneficial to establish some other ComPerMed-like structures for areas beyond NGS and molecular diagnostics, such as cancer surgery, in the face of technological and budgetary constraints for precision oncology.

Furthermore, the experts agree that the Belgian health system should focus not only on diagnosis but also on ensuring access to necessary medications for cancer care. Particularly in the case of rare cancers and their complex treatments in hospitals, collaboration with patient associations is vital. While tests to detect rare cancers are available, Belgium faces challenges in reimbursing medications for their treatment. Guidelines developed by the ComPerMed, based on evidence and expertise, are available to the NIHDI but need to be better translated into reimbursement policies. Unlike many other European countries, Phase III trials are not always feasible in Belgium for cancer medications to be approved. Engagement with the BCR would be necessary as a policy response to this scenario to explore opportunities for expanding the data collection capacity in Belgium and facilitating data sharing between countries for clinical trials in compliance with privacy regulations. Today, the BCR has a platform capable of transferring data to various institutions both within and outside Belgium, although an increased level of granularity would be preferable.

A summary of the first scenario is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Challenges and policy strategies, Scenario 1 (Source: Authors' own work)

Challenges, Scenario 1 (low budget, low technology)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges in collection of correct data • Challenges in correct interpretation of available data for drug recommendation • Challenges in referring patients to different hospitals • Challenges in demonstrating the value of treatment of rare cancers • Challenges in transfer of large data files • Lacking structured data format • Lacking data access in a federated form • Lacking accuracy when giving diagnoses due to missing (structured) data • Lacking information at the federal level about who has been tested and how
Policy strategies, Scenario 1 (low budget, low technology)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing incentives to experts to be involved in the ComPerMed • Building some other expert panels similar to the ComPerMed for cancer surgery • Reimbursing necessary medications for cancer patients (not only tests) • Enabling multi-centric Phase III clinical trials across different countries • Facilitating data sharing in compliance with privacy regulations <p>Main stakeholders: BCR, NIHDI, ComPerMed, patient associations</p>

3.2 Scenario 2 (low budget, high technology)

3.2.1 Challenges of Scenario 2

In this scenario, the Belgian health system would face pressure to maximize efficiency, striving to deliver the highest possible level of care with inadequate funding. Economic considerations would begin to dominate policy discussions, with decision-makers largely viewing medical issues only through a financial lens. Smaller hospitals and laboratories, or those with insufficient capacity, would face significant challenges. This situation could result in a centralization of health services related to precision medicine and in patients having to travel greater distances to receive cancer care. Decision-makers would become obliged to define the types of tests and treatments as well as the patient groups who should benefit from these services in a precise way.

One of the NIHDI's main concerns when recognizing treatments for reimbursement is the assumption that these treatments could be used on all patients at the same time, leading to unsustainable reimbursement mechanisms. For this reason, the NIHDI established strict

selection criteria for reimbursement, considering only certain indications. As discussed also in the first scenario, conducting Phase III trials is challenging in Belgium due to the increasing specificity of cancer cases. Consequently, it becomes difficult to demonstrate the benefits of precision medicine to NIHDI compared to standard care based only on clinical trials. In several European countries, protocols for multi-centric trials across different countries receive approval; however, this is challenging in Belgium. From an industry perspective, this issue makes the country less attractive, as the resources invested may be wasted if the trial protocols are not approved.

3.2.2 Policy strategies for Scenario 2

Stakeholders for this scenario would include i) NIHDI, given its role in reimbursement; ii) the Federal Agency for Medicine and Health Products, in consideration of its relevance to clinical trials; iii) pharmaceutical companies, whose provision of biomarkers for precision medicine can enable wider testing and greater access to medications; and iv) the surgical device and implant industry. Especially pharmaceutical companies could contribute to the financing of tests as this would increase the drug sales. A close cooperation between the industry and the NIHDI could be beneficial to this end. However, if the pharmaceutical companies assume that the cancer drugs will not be reimbursed by the NIHDI, their motivation to cover the testing could decrease. To address this challenge, studies demonstrating the evidence base for treatments are necessary, or alternative ways to make the medication accessible to patients could be explored. When discussing the reimbursement of medications for cancer patients, pharmaceutical companies understand that the market in Belgium is relatively small. Stronger collaborations with other countries such as the Netherlands and France could be beneficial, as could joining forces under European initiatives.

This scenario would moreover require the consideration of cost-effective alternatives within the health system, rather than solely focusing on additional funding to finance precision medicine. For instance, if patients need to travel greater distances for centralized services, innovative solutions such as tele-rehabilitation could be offered to allow patients to receive care at home. Another consideration could be the development of national or regional cancer programs to streamline the use of resources for procedure-specific care pathways—patient advocacy groups could lead such an initiative. In this way, the health system could benefit from

available resources in the most efficient way, fostering collaboration between the regions and avoiding parallel initiatives with overlaps.

A summary of the second scenario is provided in Table 4.

Table 4. Challenges and policy strategies, Scenario 2 (Source: Authors' own work)

Challenges, Scenario 2 (low budget, high technology)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges resulting from cost-efficiency orientation in the health system • Challenges in adapting fast-changing field of precision medicine when conducting cost-benefit analyses • Challenges in defining precise indications and eligibility criteria for reimbursement • Challenges in instrumentalizing evidence-based medicine to rationalize healthcare costs • Challenges for certain hospitals and laboratories that may not meet demands, leading to centralization of health services (thus, longer distance for patients to travel) • Challenges resulting from inequalities in access to healthcare
Policy strategies, Scenario 2 (low budget, high technology)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seizing the opportunity for telemedicine • Involving patient organizations in the policymaking process • Ensuring collaboration between the industry and public sector to lower the costs for necessary medications • Avoiding sequential testing for more efficient use of resources • Collaborating with other European countries to join forces for conducting research <p>Main stakeholders: NIHDI, Federal Agency for Health Products, pharmaceutical and medical technology industries, patient associations</p>

3.3 Scenario 3 (high budget, low technology)

3.3.1 Challenges of Scenario 3

Given low-quality data, this scenario would lead to inaccurate diagnoses, eventually contributing to higher health expenses. In oncology, hospitals must operate swiftly; long waiting periods for months can cause serious harms to cancer patients. Despite ample budget in the health system and high-quality tests, a lack of IT infrastructure and inefficient referral pathways could result in late diagnoses and worsening patient outcomes. If infrastructural constraints cause extensive delays, patients fail to receive the right treatment at the right time, leading to a reduction in the number of curable patients and an increased demand for palliative

care in the health system. Even if the initial diagnosis is correct, inadequate IT infrastructure can negatively affect the cancer care trajectory of patients.

Hence, in this scenario, a considerable challenge would be the referrals of patients to specialized cancer centers. In the absence of data standardization, patients may receive tests in one center and be referred elsewhere as their disease progresses. If the referral system is dysfunctional, difficulties arise in gathering information for collaborative treatments. In the absence of data standardization, effective patient pathways may become difficult. Moreover, comparing cancer patients for benchmarking and tracking their progress may be problematic without the necessary data standardization and IT infrastructure. Ultimately, this situation would result in declining patient confidence in the health system and a tendency of patients to overestimate the potential of technology, creating unrealistic expectations (believing better technology could have solved all health problems).

3.3.2 Policy strategies for Scenario 3

In the face of low standardization of protocols, test and nomenclature across hospitals and laboratories, this scenario would lead to disproportionate spending of financial resources in process optimization. While healthcare researchers mostly strive to implement evidence-based solutions in clinical care, the NIHDI tends to prioritize the large-scale impact and demonstrable results at the population level. Even today, with the absence of a standard procedure across Belgium, different tests are being offered in different hospitals. As translating national guidelines into practice is often hindered in bureaucratic procedures, hospitals start implementing different standards independently from each other. The situation would worsen in this third scenario with lacking standardization of protocols, tests, and nomenclature, as it would be crucial for research findings to be uniformly translated into clinical practice.

To harmonize protocols and testing procedures across the country, Belgium needs an efficient governance structure. This governance challenge results mainly from the country's federated structure and requires the collaboration of all relevant stakeholders. The optimal solution would require a collaborative effort between the NIHDI, companies, medical professionals like oncologists, and patients. Notably, achieving consensus among them can be difficult. Nonetheless, the ComPerMed, with its multi-disciplinary structure, could serve as a blueprint in this context. Moreover, the opportunity to gather evidence through clinical trials from

different countries could contribute to better decision-making. If Health Technology Assessments (HTAs) in other European countries could be reported accurately and transparently, their insights would be beneficial also for Belgium.

A summary of the third scenario is provided in Table 5.

Table 5. Challenges and policy strategies, Scenario 3 (Source: Authors' own work)

Challenges, Scenario 3 (high budget, low technology)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges in collecting correct data • Challenges resulting from inefficient data flow and subpar IT infrastructure • Challenges resulting from inefficient use of resources in the health system • Lacking data standardization to guide healthcare professionals • Lacking certainty about whether patients are receiving the right treatment at the right time
Policy strategies, Scenario 3 (high budget, low technology)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimizing the data standardization process • Identifying better biomarkers and ensuring their clinical use • Providing guidance to patients and healthcare professionals about the meaningful use of technologies for precision medicine • Ensuring better governance for effective decision-making • Mapping available Health Technology Assessments (HTAs) in other European countries <p>Main stakeholders: NIHDI, Federal Agency for Health Products, medical technology industry, Belgian Health Care Knowledge Centre (KCE), expert groups in oncology such as Belgian Hematology Society, patient associations</p>

3.4 Scenario 4 (high budget, high technology)

3.4.1 Challenges of Scenario 4

In this scenario, the greatest risk would be over-testing and over-treatment of patients, driven by the abundance of available financial resources and technology. The health system may neglect the real needs of patients, offering technology as the main solution to their health problems. Due to increased awareness about the available technology, patients could request “me-too” screening and diagnostic testing with low performance, despite their minimal benefits. For instance, diagnosis of a hereditary cancer syndrome without appropriate follow-up can evoke fear in patients. Similarly, incidental findings can cause health complications:

Following the increased number of treatments, concerns arising from unnecessary surgery of benign tumors and the adverse outcomes following surgery can be observed.

As a result, patients can be harmed with psychological distress, side effects of medications and complications due to over-treatment if professional education or medical guidelines fall short. Over-testing within the population may not only lead to side effects but also drive up healthcare costs even further. If financial resources were infinite, even incidental findings could be treated under certain circumstances. However, these resources would be better directed to areas with an impact at a larger scale. If the health system neglects to apply effective public health measures, prioritizing precision medicine over primary prevention could become problematic from an ethical viewpoint.

3.4.2 Policy strategies for Scenario 4

In this scenario, patient advocacy groups would assume a significant role to fully comprehend the impact of incidental findings and overutilization of genetic testing on patients. In addition, to reduce potential over-testing, over-treatment and over-spending, health quality institutes such as the *Vlaams Instituut voor Kwaliteit van Zorg* (VIKZ; Flemish Institute for Quality and Care) would be relevant. Ideally, a dialogue should be initiated with the BCR, considering its collaboration with the VIKZ and the Belgian Health Care Knowledge Centre (KCE) for evidence-based solutions so that the system does not reward overactivity. As the health system broadens access to services with cutting-edge technology, better governance and clinical guidelines would be imperative. Educating patients and healthcare professionals on when to conduct testing or treatment would be crucial. In this context, expert panels to make decisions regarding incidental findings would also be essential.

A summary of the fourth scenario is provided in Table 6.

Table 6. Challenges and policy strategies, Scenario 4 (Source: Authors' own work)

Challenges, Scenario 4 (high budget, high technology)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges resulting from unnecessary testing for cancer • Challenges resulting from over-diagnosis and over-treatments of incidental findings • Challenges in ensuring the right level of knowledge and expertise about patient safety among the healthcare professionals ("first do not harm") • Challenges resulting from the need of developing patient safety guidelines, alongside numerous others • Challenges in answering difficult ethical questions such as dying of cancer vs. dying with cancer • Challenges resulting from prioritization of precision medicine (is there enough budget available also for other diseases and treatment options?) • Challenges resulting from a tunnel vision that may neglect the patients' real needs
Policy strategies, Scenario 4 (high budget, high technology)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing guidance to patients and healthcare professionals on the better use of resources • Involving patient associations and expert groups in decision-making • Ensuring patient safety and quality in healthcare to take measures against over-testing and over-treatment <p>Main stakeholders: NIHDI, Belgian Health Care Knowledge Centre (KCE), patient associations, health quality institutes such as <i>Vlaams Instituut voor Kwaliteit van Zorg</i> (VIKZ; Flemish Institute for Quality and Care), expert groups in oncology such as Belgian Hematology Society</p>

4 Discussion

With the increasing prevalence and incidence of cancer cases in Belgium, several factors must be considered for implementing precision oncology in routine care. Our foresight workshops focused mainly on the financial coverage and the infrastructure for data collection, quality, storage, transfer, and processing to facilitate the implementation. In terms of reimbursement, it became clear that generating evidence on the innovative approaches in cancer treatment could be challenging in Belgium. Studies show that the demand for a rigid evidence base for reimbursement can be problematic in health systems when Phase III trials are unachievable or even not necessary (van der Velden *et al.*, 2019). Promoting collaborative research, employing observational studies, and exploring alternative reimbursement strategies can help when addressing this issue (van der Velden *et al.*, 2019). Another solution could be diagnostic-specific value-assessment and flexible pricing over time for a wider coverage of precision

medicine among the population (Towse and Garrison, 2017). This approach could allow for reduced initial costs and dynamic adjustments as real-world evidence emerges, making precision medicine more accessible. In addition, adequate infrastructure to enable data linkages with cancer registries and administrative health data could support stratification strategies for more effective tailoring of treatments or interventions (Tarricone *et al.*, 2021).

However, beyond budgetary issues and necessary IT infrastructure for high-quality data storage and exchange, our results also show that there is no “silver bullet” that could offer an ideal solution, and none of the four future scenarios is exempt from drawbacks. Even the fourth one (high budget, high technology—seemingly the most ideal scenario) was taken with caution by the experts. Recent literature on the use of AI in European health systems also note that the available technological solutions can do harm if they are overused or misused and increase costs for healthcare even more without necessarily improving the health outcomes of patients (European Commission, 2024). Mitigating the downsides of each scenario thus requires targeted strategies, such as seizing the opportunity for telemedicine in Scenario 2 and ensuring patient safety and quality in care in Scenario 4. In addition, each foresight scenario needs policy responses that should go beyond economic and technological considerations, such as the involvement of patient associations and public or the engagement of multi-disciplinary groups in precision medicine and data governance.

Generally speaking, the implementation of precision medicine in health systems requires not only extensive knowledge in genomic medicine and health informatics, but also in social engagement and implementation, which are mostly specific to individual countries (Horgan, 2018). Indeed, precision medicine relies on access to vast amounts of health data, with patient and public support being crucial for successful and sustainable policies (Kaye, 2012). In Belgium, studies demonstrating trustworthiness when collecting and sharing genomic data highlight the importance of transparency in data handling (Mayeur *et al.*, 2021; Milne *et al.*, 2021). Communication with the public should emphasize the potential benefits of genomics research, identify the recipients of these benefits, and outline the mechanisms through which they can be realized (Milne *et al.*, 2021). Nonetheless, when doing so, public engagement should also be framed as an opportunity to listen to and learn from citizens’ perspectives rather than imposing predefined ideas or educating them (Mayeur *et al.*, 2024). As recent European laws, such as the AI Act or the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS), redefine data governance frameworks and call for implementation by a broad range of institutional actors,

ensuring coordination will likely become a challenge at the national level (Schmitt *et al.*, 2023). Here, the ComPerMed can serve as a foundation for the coordination of multi-disciplinary expert groups on genomic data governance and translational medicine (Aguilera-Cobos *et al.*, 2022). The role of public engagement and expert panels becomes even more significant when integrating AI into precision oncology, as they help address ethical concerns, build trust, and guide responsible implementation.

Nonetheless, it is also important to note that even though AI could eventually become a reality in precision oncology in Belgium, some considerations should be kept in mind. Research on precision medicine highlights the risks posed by structural inequities that privilege some groups while disadvantaging others and addresses broader concerns such as potential biases due to ethnicity, geography or ability to pay (McGuire *et al.*, 2020). AI algorithms trained only with a narrow set of data from certain population groups, might not be able to detect cancer cases in other (excluded) groups, known also as “rubbish in–rubbish out” (Janssens *et al.*, 2018). In addition, a patient’s ethnicity is mostly determined by their self-reporting or appearance, which may not reflect their genetic background accurately. Hence, while AI models perform well in controlled environments with homogeneous data, their real-world performance may fall short of expectations (European Commission, 2024). In the face of significant concerns about equity and social justice, the consequences of under-representation of traditionally underserved groups in genomic research can become even more pronounced. One potential solution to this imbalance could be generating synthetic data that mirrors the distributions and variances of real-world data and using simulated environments (D’Amico *et al.*, 2023; Johnson *et al.*, 2021). In this way, Belgium could harness AI’s transformative potential in precision oncology while fostering equitable and effective cancer care for all.

As part of a foresight exercise, this study presented the qualitative outcomes of two expert workshops. Despite its benefits, the study faces some limitations. Admittedly, it relies on the insights from a relatively small group of country experts, potentially reducing the generalizability of our findings. Moreover, the self-selection of participants may have introduced biases, as those who chose to participate might not represent the full range of relevant perspectives. Furthermore, the identification of challenges and policy formulation processes largely depended on expert interpretation, reflecting subjective judgments. While the structured approach and facilitation by a moderator experienced in precision medicine aimed

to ensure balanced input from the participants, group dynamics in the second workshop may have influenced which ideas were emphasized or refined. Nonetheless, our study offers a contextually rich exploration of precision oncology in Belgium, potentially laying the groundwork for future research and fostering policy discussions on this promising field.

5 Conclusion

This study highlighted the complexities of the implementation of precision oncology and the use of AI in the Belgian health system. Employing a foresight methodology, country experts discussed four distinct scenarios for integrating precision oncology into routine care in the future. Our findings underscore the need for improved data infrastructure and addressing the challenges of HTA in precision oncology, particularly for rare cancers. We conclude that each scenario has its own unique challenges, hence refrain from imposing any hierarchy between them. Although no single approach offers a comprehensive solution to these scenarios, we strongly recommend multidisciplinary collaboration and public engagement as essential components of precision oncology, particularly when using AI in this context. With AI driving transformation in health data processing worldwide, proactive consideration of challenges and policy solutions can equip Belgium for resilient, future-oriented cancer care.

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